

Organic Iodides *via* Organocopper Reagents and Iodine

M. T. RAHMAN* and H. GILMAN

Department of Chemistry, Iowa State University, Ames, Iowa 50010, U. S. A.

Manuscript received 18 October 1973 ; accepted 1 August 1974

Alkyl, aryl and perhaloaryl iodides have been prepared in 64-94% yields by the iodination of the corresponding copper reagents. The yields of the aryl and perhaloaryl iodides by this method are higher than those obtained by the iodination of the corresponding Grignard reagents. Other methods have been compared. Some preliminary studies have been made on the relative reactivities of various arylcopper reagents with iodine.

IN connection with our studies concerning the synthesis of thermally stable polyfunctional monomers, we report here the preparation of some aryl, alkyl and perhaloaryl iodides from the corresponding copper reagents and iodine. Although in recent years considerable interest has been shown in organocopper (I) reagents** and the corresponding 'ate'^{6,7} complexes for their versatility as reagents in organic synthesis, relatively little is known about their reaction with iodine. Wittig^{7,8} reported that certain cuprates react with iodine to give the corresponding iodides in good yields. *e.g.*, lithium *o*-quaterphenylcuprate produces diiodo-*ortho*-quaterphenyl in 55% yield. More recently Corey and Katzenellenbogen⁹ mentioned that 3-methyl-2-coppermethyldecanoate, subsequent to iodination, gives the corresponding iodo compound in 'high yield'. But so far no detailed studies have been made on the synthetic potentialities of the iodination reactions of organocopper reagents and their 'ate' complexes. We describe below the results of our examination of these copper reagents as potential sources of aryl and perhaloaryl iodides.

Experimental :

The reactions described here were conducted in an oxygen-free, dry nitrogen atmosphere. The

solvents were dried over sodium wire and further purified by distillation from sodium-benzophenone ketyl. *n*-Butyllithium in hexane, methyl lithium in ether and phenyllithium in ether-benzene were from the Foote Mineral Co. These lithium reagents were used at the strength determined by the supplier. Anhydrous copper(I) chloride (A.R. Grade) was from Mallinckrodt Chemical Works and was purified¹⁰ prior to use. Anhydrous copper(I) bromide was prepared¹¹ and purified by a method similar to the one used for the purification of copper (I) chloride. Copper(I) iodide was from Alfa Inorganic Chemicals and was used without further purification. Glc analyses were carried out on an F and M model 500 Gas Chromatograph, using a 4' column, packed with 15% Silicone Gum Rubber on Chromosorb W (60-80 mesh) unless otherwise mentioned. The yields were computed on the amount of starting polyhaloarenes ; in the case of a product containing phenyl, methyl or *n*-butyl groups the computations were based on the amount of the respective starting lithium reagents. All temperature, quoted are uncorrected.

Preparation of various organometallic reagents :

The pentachlorophenylmagnesium chloride¹² and the corresponding lithium¹³ and copper^{5, 14, 15} reagents, tetrachloro-4-pyridylmagnesium chloride¹⁶ and the corresponding copper reagent¹⁷, pentafluorophenylmagnesium chloride¹⁸ and the corresponding lithium¹⁹ and copper¹⁸ reagents, trichloro-2-thienylmagnesium halide²⁰ and the corresponding copper²¹ reagent were prepared by following the published procedures.

* Department of Chemistry, The University of Dacca, Dacca-2, Bangladesh.

** Although the organocopper(I) reagents may exist as associated structures (*e.g.*, tetramer¹) and form complexes²⁻⁴ with solvent molecules as ligands, for simplicity they will be referred to as organocopper reagents.

Methylcopper²² and *n*-butylcopper²³ were prepared by slow addition of a selected organolithium reagent (*x* moles) to copper(I) iodide (*x* moles) in diethyl ether at -15° and stirring the mixture until Colour Test I²⁴ was negative. Phenylcopper^{2, 25} was prepared from phenyllithium and various copper(I) halides in diethyl ether and tetrahydrofuran (THF). Table 1 shows the yields of iodobenzene and hence probably of phenylcopper under different experimental conditions.

Lithium dimethylcuprate²², lithium di-*n*-butylcuprate²³ and lithium diphenylcuprate^{26, 27} were prepared according to the published methods which consisted of the dropwise addition of an appropriate organolithium reagent (2*x* moles) to copper(I) iodide (*x* moles) at -15° . Chloromagnesium *bis*(pentafluorophenyl) cuprate was prepared (on a 0.5 molar scale) in a similar manner using penta-

sulphate. The solid obtained after the removal of solvent was further purified by chromatography on a silica gel column and/or by subsequent recrystallisation from carbon tetrachloride. Further experimental details are given in Table 2.

Following this procedure, pentachloroiodobenzene, m.p. 210° (cited²⁸; 207.5° - 208°) from pentachlorophenylcopper; tetrachloro-4-iodopyridine, m.p. 201° - 202° (cited²⁹; 202°) from tetrachloro-4-pyridylcopper; trichloro-2-iodothiophene, m.p. 49° - 50° (cited³⁰; 50° - 51°) from trichloro-2-thienylcopper; pentafluoroiodobenzene, b.p. 76° - $78^{\circ}/35$ mm, $n_D^{20} 1.4955$ (cited³¹; 77° - $78^{\circ}/35$ mm, $n_D^{20} 1.4965^{32}$) from pentafluorophenylcopper, were prepared. The identification of the iodides was completed by comparing their m.p., ir and glc analyses data with those iodides obtained by the iodination of the appropriate Grignard reagents.

TABLE 1—IODINATION* OF PHENYLCOPPER PREPARED UNDER DIFFERENT CONDITIONS

RLi (0.05 M)	CuX (0.05 M)	Solvent	RCu Prepd. at $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Iodination temp. $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Products, Yield (%)	
					RI	R-R
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Li}$	CuCl	Ether	0	-78	0-14	70-80
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Li}$	CuCl	Ether	-15	-78	39-43	51-56
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Li}$	CuCl	THF	-15	-78	94	3
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Li}$	CuCl	THF	-15	0	87	4
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Li}$	CuBr	Ether	0	-78	91	2
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Li}$	CuI	Ether	0	-78	87	8
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Li}$	CuI	Ether	-15	-78	87-90	7-9
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Li}$	CuI	THF	-15	-78	91	2
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Li}$	CuI	THF	-15	-78	87**	7**

* Solid iodine (one equivalent) in bulk and at one time was added unless otherwise mentioned.

** Iodine in THF-benzene was added dropwise for iodination.

fluorophenylmagnesium chloride in place of the lithium reagent. It did not respond to Colour Test I²⁴. Lithium *bis*(pentafluorophenyl)cuprate and its pentachlorophenyl analogue were prepared from the respective lithium reagents in the same way except that the reaction temperature was -78° instead of -15° . Lithium *bis*(pentafluorophenyl)cuprate did not give Colour Test I, whereas lithium *bis*(pentachlorophenyl) cuprate did under related conditions.

Iodination of perhaloaryl copper reagents: Solid iodine (*x* moles) was added all at one time to a perhaloaryl copper reagent prepared from a perhaloarene (*x* moles). The reaction mixture was stirred at the ambient temperature for 2 hr, hydrolysed with ammonium chloride-aqueous ammonia solution, extracted with ether or benzene, and the ether or benzene extract was dried over anhydrous sodium

TABLE 2—IODINATION OF PERHALOARYLCOPPER REAGENTS PREPARED UNDER DIFFERENT CONDITIONS

RM (0.5 M) in THF	CuX (0.05 M)	RCu Prepd. at $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Iodina- tion temp. $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Products (Yield %)	
				RI	R-R
$\text{C}_6\text{Cl}_5\text{Li}$	CuCl	-78	27	80	4
$\text{C}_6\text{Cl}_5\text{Li}$	CuCl	-78	27	76*	—
$\text{C}_6\text{Cl}_5\text{Li}$	CuI	-78	27	78	10
$\text{C}_6\text{Cl}_5\text{MgCl}$	CuCl	0	27	77	5
$\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{MgCl}$	CuCl	0	0	84	8
$\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{MgCl}$	CuI	0	0	72-73	9-11
$\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{MgCl}$	CuI	0	0	75**	7**
$\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{Li}$	CuI	-78	0	77	11
$\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{MgCl}$	CuI	0	-78	70	9
$(4\text{-C}_6\text{Cl}_4\text{N})\text{MgCl}$	CuCl	-10	0	77	—
$(2\text{-C}_6\text{Cl}_4\text{S})\text{MgX}$	CuCl	0	27	85	2

* 30% excess iodine was employed for the iodination.

** Iodine in THF- C_6H_6 was added dropwise to iodinate $\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{Cu}$.

Iodination of phenylcopper reagents: Phenylcopper reagents were prepared and iodinated under various conditions (Table 1), the technique of iodination being the same as before. The maximum yield (94%) of iodobenzene was obtained when the phenylcopper reagent was prepared from phenyllithium and copper (I) chloride in THF at -15° and iodinated at -78° (b.p. 84° - 86° /35 mm, n_D^{20} 1.6163; cited^{3a}; b.p. 187.7° , n_D^{18-20} 1.618).

Iodination of alkylcopper reagents: Methyl and *n*-butylcopper reagents were iodinated in the same way as before except that the iodination temperature was -78° . The reaction mixture was stirred at this temperature for 2 hr and then allowed to come to room temperature slowly. The products were estimated by glc (4', 5% Crosslinked Diethylene Glycol Adipate, LAC-446, on Fluoropak, 80 mesh) using *n*-heptane as an internal standard. The yields of the respective alkyl iodides are mentioned in Table 3.

Iodination of 'ate' complexes: All 'ate' complexes were iodinated at -78° by the addition of solid iodine (two equivalents) in bulk and at one time. The mixture was stirred at -78° for 1 hr and allowed to come to room temperature slowly. The work-up procedures were similar to those for the respective simple copper reagents. The yields of the various iodides by this method are shown in Table 3.

Iodination of perhaloarylmagnesium halides: The Grignard reagents were prepared on a 0.05 molar scale as mentioned above, and added to iodine (0.05 mole) in benzene (100 ml) or to solid iodine (0.05 mole). The reverse addition was also tried. Pentachlorophenylmagnesium chloride and trichloro-2-thienylmagnesium halide were iodinated at 0° , whereas tetrachloro-4-pyridylmagnesium chloride was iodinated at -10° because of its poor¹⁶ thermal stability. After the addition was complete the mixture was generally stirred for 2 hr at room temperature, hydrolysed with dilute hydrochloric acid, and the products extracted in ether (in the case of the iodination of trichloro-2-thienylmagnesium halide) or in benzene for all other reactions). The various iodides were purified in the same way as before. The yields by both direct and reverse addition methods are shown in Table 3.

Reactions of perhaloarenes with anhydrous sodium iodide: A mixture of hexachlorobenzene (0.05 mole) and anhydrous sodium iodide (4×0.05 moles) in dry acetone (275 ml) was refluxed for 12 hr, cooled to room temperature, and digested with water. The organic material was then extracted in benzene and recrystallised to give the starting hexachlorobenzene (90-95%). 95% Hexachlorobenzene was also recovered from the above reaction when the reaction was conducted in dimethylformamide (DMF) for 48 hr. A similar treatment of tetrachlorothiophene in either acetone or DMF did not produce any iodide, and 98% of the starting material was recovered. Pentachloropyridine was also unaffected by a similar treatment in acetone, but in DMF for 48 hr 6% tetrachloro-4-iodopyridine (m.p. 202° , cited^{3a}: 202°) and 80% of the starting pentachloropyridine were obtained.

Results and Discussion

Iodination of aryl- and perhaloarylcopper reagents with iodine gives the corresponding aromatic iodides in 74-94% yields (Table 3). The method appears to

TABLE 3—IODINATION* OF VARIOUS ORGANOMETALLIC REAGENTS

R	Yields (%) of RI via		
	RMgX	RCu	LiR ₃ Cu
C ₆ H ₅	90 ^{3a}	94 (3) [†] 90 (6) [‡]	— 86 (12) [‡]
C ₆ F ₅	46.7 ^{3a}	84 (8) 77 (11)	— 59 (28), 47 (37) [§]
C ₆ Cl ₅	70, 65 [*]	80 (4) 78 (10)	 61 (22)
(4-C ₆ Cl ₄ N)	67 [*] , 65	74	—
(2-C ₆ Cl ₄ S)	66-70, 63	83 (2)	—
CH ₃	—	65-70	50-60
<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	—	64 (24)	46 (52)

* Iodinated by adding solid iodine in bulk unless otherwise mentioned.

^{||} The Grignard reagent was added to iodine in benzene unless otherwise mentioned.

[†] The figures in parentheses represent the yields of the coupling products, R-R.

[‡] The yields from the reactions (involving copper reagents) carried out under the same conditions are on the same horizontal line.

[§] The figures in bold type indicate the yields by iodinating $\text{ClMg}(\text{C}_6\text{F}_5)_2\text{Cu}$, prepared from $\text{CuI} + 2\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{MgCl}$ in THF.

= The figures in italic represent the yields when a solution of iodine in benzene was added to the Grignard reagent.

+ When tetrachloro-4-pyridylmagnesium chloride was added to solid iodine the yield of RI was 54%. When solid iodine was added in bulk to the Grignard reagent RI was formed in 48% yield.

be general since both homocyclic and heterocyclic aromatic iodides have been prepared. Alkyl iodides have also been prepared in 64-75% yields, but there are better methods of preparing them in even higher yields³⁵.

Employing our method we have prepared iodo-benzene (I), pentafluoriodobenzene (II), pentachloro-iodobenzene (III), tetrachloro-4-iodopyridine (IV), trichloro-2-iodothiophene (V) and 3,4-dichloro-2,5-diiodothiophene (VI)³⁶. These iodides could not be prepared by heating a mixture of perchloro- or perfluoroarene and sodium iodide—a method which has proved very successful for the preparation of some other aryl and perhaloaryl iodides^{37,38}. The iodides (II-VI), however, were prepared by another conventional method, iodination of the Grignard reagents^{34,39}. The procedure consists in the addition of the Grignard reagent to an iodine solution. This 'reverse' as against 'direct' addition, we have confirmed, gives better yields³⁴. But the 'reverse' addition is rather inconvenient particularly when one is dealing with thermally unstable Grignard reagents *e.g.*, tetrachloro-4-pyridylmagnesium chloride. On the other hand, the copper reagents are relatively more stable⁴⁰. The iodination of copper reagents is very simple and consists in the direct addition of iodine in bulk and at one time to the copper reagents. Thus the difficulty in handling the unstable Grignard reagents and the inconvenience of the reverse addition are avoided. Moreover, as is obvious from Table 3, the yields of the iodides *via* the copper reagents are 10-37% greater than those *via* the Grignard reagents. Our method for the preparation of perhaloaryl iodides, therefore, seems to be better.

The iodination of simple copper reagents gives better yields of iodides than the iodination of the corresponding lithium diorganocuprates (Table 3). These cuprates^{6,7} form coupling products in high yields. The following is a probable mechanism for the formation of the coupling products during the iodination of cuprates.

The detailed mechanism of reaction (1) may be similar to the one proposed by Corey and Posner^{33,41}, and also by Whitesides and coworkers³⁶ for the alkylation^{33,36,41-43} or arylation^{36,43} of organic iodides. However, the oxidative coupling of

the 'ate' complexes in the presence of iodine may also account for the increased yields of the coupling products. The simple copper compounds, which being much poorer^{4,30} nucleophiles than the corresponding 'ate' complexes, react slowly with organic iodides under moderate conditions. This may explain the formation of smaller amounts of the coupling products during the iodination of simple copper reagents. Part of the coupling products obtained during the iodination of the relatively unstable alkylcopper reagents, however, may have originated from the thermal decomposition⁴⁴ of these reagents.

The iodination of the 'ate' complexes appears to take place in steps. Thus, when a faintly coloured but clear²² solution of lithium dimethylcuprate was iodinated by the slow addition of iodine, bright yellow precipitates characteristic³⁹ of methylcopper began to appear. The yellow precipitates seemed to be produced in a maximum yield when approximately one equivalent of iodine was added. The precipitates started disappearing as the second equivalent of the iodine was added slowly. Finally, a clear brownish solution was obtained. This may indicate that the first step of the reaction is the formation of a simple copper reagent (yellow precipitates), which then reacts further with another molecule of iodine giving a colourless iodide. Thus for lithium dimethylcuprate the following mechanism may be proposed :

Since different organocopper reagents may be formed under different experimental conditions^{2,15}, we investigated the relative reactivity of a copper reagent prepared from different starting materials. The iodination of copper reagents prepared from either the Grignard or the lithium reagent and copper (I) chloride in THF gave essentially similar yields of the iodides (Table 2). Similarly, the iodination of phenylcopper, prepared from equivalent amounts of phenyllithium and copper (I) bromide or iodide in ether gave comparable yields of iodo-benzene (Table 1). These results demonstrated the similar reactivities of reagents prepared from different starting materials.

During this study we observed that phenylcopper, prepared from phenyllithium and copper (I) chloride in ether at 0°, is unstable and decomposes to biphenyl and metallic copper if kept standing at this tempera-

ture. This reagent when iodinated immediately after preparation at 0°, gives up to a 14% yield of iodobenzene and 80% of biphenyl. If the reagent is prepared at -15°, the yield of iodobenzene increases to 43% and that of biphenyl decreases to 56%. When the phenylcopper reagent is prepared as above in THF rather than in ether, apparently a stable copper reagent is formed and the iodination of the reagent affords iodobenzene in 94% yield. From the foregoing it appears that the thermal stability of a phenylcopper reagent (or its complex²⁻⁶) depends on the type of solvent and copper (I) halide employed to prepare it (Table I). If the copper(I) chloride is used for the preparation of phenylcopper then THF should be used to increase its stability. Ether may be used as a solvent if copper (I) bromide or iodide is employed to prepare the copper reagent. It has been observed previously that considerable amounts of hexachloro-2, 2'-bithienyl and perfluorobiphenyl are obtained during the preparation of trichloro-2-thienylcopper²¹ and pentafluorophenylcopper¹⁴, respectively, from the corresponding lithium reagents and copper (I) chloride in ether. The yields of the biaryls, however, were insignificant when THF was used in place of ether. We believe that these biaryls (as is biphenyl mentioned above) are formed in part by the decomposition of the thermally unstable copper reagents prepared in ether. It may, therefore, seem generally true that an arylcopper reagent is less stable if prepared from copper (I) chloride in ether and that its stability may be considerably increased if a strong donor solvent like THF is used instead of ether.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by the United States Air Force under Contract No. F33615-69-C-1046 monitored by the Air Force Materials Laboratory, Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio.

References

1. A. Cairncross and W. A. Sheppard., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 93, 247 and 248.
2. G. Costa, A. Camus, L. Gatti and N. Marsich., *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 568.
3. A. Camus and N. Marsich., *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1970, 21, 249.
4. H. O. House, W. L. Respass and G. M. Whitesides., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, 31, 3128; H. O. House and W. F. Fischer, Jr., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, 33, 949.
5. A. Cairncross and W. A. Sheppard., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 2186.
6. W. Tochtermann, *Angew. Chem., Internat. Ed.*, 1966, 5, 351.
7. G. Wittig, *Quart. Rev.*, 1966, 20, 191.
8. G. Wittig and G. Lehmann, *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, 90, 875; G. Wittig and F. Bickelhaupt, *Chem. Ber.*, 1958, 91, 883; G. Klar, *Dissertation*, Heidelberg, 1964.
9. E. J. Corey and J. A. Katzenellenbogen., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 1851.
10. R. N. Keller and H. D. Wycoff, *Inorg. Syn.*, 1946, 2, 1.
11. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd Edition, Longmans, London, 1961, p. 191.
12. H. Gilman and Sze-Yuen Sim., *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1967, 7, 249.
13. S. D. Rosenberg, J. J. Walburn and H. E. Ramsden. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 1606.
14. A. E. Jukes, S. S. Dua and H. Gilman., *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1970, 21, 241.
15. R. J. Dey Pasquale and C. Tamborski., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, 34, 1736.
16. S. S. Dua and H. Gilman., *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1968, 12, 234.
17. S. S. Dua, A. E. Jukes and H. Gilman., *Org. Prep. Proced.*, 1969, 1, 187.
18. A. E. Jukes and H. Gilman, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1969, 17, 145.
19. R. J. Harper, Jr., E. J. Soloski and C. Tamborski., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 29, 2385.
20. M. T. Rahman, M. R. Smith Jr., A. F. Webb and H. Gilman., *Organometal. Chem. Syn.*, 1970/1971, 1, 105.
21. M. R. Smith Jr., M. T. Rahman and H. Gilman., *Organometal. Chem. Syn.*, 1971, 1, 295.
22. H. Gilman, R. G. Jones and L. A. Woods., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 1630.
23. E. J. Corey and G. H. Posner., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 5615.
24. H. Gilman and F. Schulze., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2032. See also particularly, H. Gilman and H. L. Yablunsky. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 839. U. Schöllkopf, Houben Weyl, XIII/I, Thieme Verlag, Stuttgart, 1970 (for three colour tests).
25. H. Gilman and J. M. Straley. *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas*, 1936, 55, 821.
26. G. M. Whitesides, W. F. Fischer, Jr., J. San Filippo, Jr., R. W. Bashe and H. O. House., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 4871.
27. G. M. Whitesides, J. San Filippo, Jr., C. P. Casey and E. J. Panek, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 5302.
28. M. Istrati., *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1891, 5, 169.
29. R. C. Edmondson and H. Gilman., unpublished studies.
30. W. Steinkopf and W. Köhler., *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1937, 532, 250.
31. W. J. Pummer and L. A. Wall., U. S. Patent, 3046, 313; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, 57, 15003.

RAHMAN & GILMAN : ORGANIC IODINES VIA ORGANOCOPPER REAGENTS & IODINE

32. N. N. Vorozhtsov, Jr., V. A. Barkhash, N. G. Ivanova, S. A. Anichkina and O. I. Andreevskaya., *Dokl. Akad. Nauk (SSSR)*, 1964, **159**, 125.
33. W. H. Perkin., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, **69** 1249 ; K. Seubert, *Chem. Ber.*, 1889, **22**, 2519.
34. R. L. Datta and H. K. Mitter., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 287.
35. R. T. Morrison and R. N. Boyd., "Organic Chemistry", Allyn and Bacon Inc., Boston, 2nd Ed., 1966. p. 462 ; I. L. Finar, "Organic Chemistry", Vol. 1, Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd., London, 3rd Ed., 1959, p 93-97.
36. M. R. Smith, Jr., and H. Gilman., *J. Organometal. Chem.* 1972, **42**, 1.
37. R. E. Banks, R. N. Haszeldine, E. Phillips and I. M. Young., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **C**, 2091.
38. J. F. Bunnet and R. M. Conner., *Org. Syn.*, 1960, **40**, 34 ; L. A. Wall and J. M. Antonucci., U. S. Patent, 1970, no. 3, 499,046 ; A. M. Killop, J. S. Fowler, M. J. Zalesco, J. D. Hunt, E. C. Taylor and G. McGillivray, *Tetraheiron Letters*, 1969, **29**, 2427.
39. L. I. Zakharkin, V. V. Gavrilenko and B. A. Paley. *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1970, **21**, 269 ; and the references therein.
40. A. E. Jukes, S. S. Dua and H. Gilman., *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1970, **24**, 791.
41. E. J. Corey and G. H. Posner., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967 **89**, 3911.
42. G. Büchi and J. A. Carlson., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 5336.
43. E. J. Corey, J. A. Katzenellenbogen, N. W. Gilman, S. A. Roman and B. W. Erickson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 5618.
44. G. Costa and G. De Alti, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1957, **87**, 1273 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, **52**, 19452 ; C. E. H. Bawn and F. J. Whitby, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3926 ; G. Costa, A. Camus and N. Marsich, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* 1965, **27**, 281.